

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH. BEST PRACTICES FOR LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *In the article you will find a description of various approaches to teaching English to students. The topic will be useful for young teachers and those who want to learn the language on their own. It is important for the consumer to understand how his language needs are met.*

Key words: *methodology, beginning, identifier, lexicography, syntax, Methodology.*

МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ. ЛУЧШИЕ ПРАКТИКИ ДЛЯ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В статье вы найдете описание различных подходов к обучению студентов английскому языку. Тема будет полезна молодым учителям и тем, кто хочет выучить язык самостоятельно. Потребителю важно понимать, как удовлетворяются его языковые потребности.*

Ключевые слова: *методология, начало, идентификатор, лексикография, синтаксис, Методология.*

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge level In order for a teacher to understand which method of teaching English he chooses for his classes, it is necessary to have an idea about the levels of knowledge of the language.

- Elementary - entry level. The student has enough knowledge to understand simple phrases, instructions. Can participate in simple dialogues. The student understands simple texts with a limited vocabulary, can write elementary phrases and sentences.

- Pre-Intermediate... A student with below-intermediate knowledge can express their wants, thoughts, and needs. Can understand simple texts, including basic vocabulary, can form sentences with personal information.

- Average skill level or Medium. The student can express his opinion on certain topics, participate in conversations. It becomes much easier for such students to understand texts, the ability to learn new vocabulary from the context appears. Can write simple texts with rationale, using familiar vocabulary.

- Upper-intermediate . At this level of proficiency, the student can discuss various topics, including technical terminology. Understands general information and details when working with text, context continues to play a supporting role in learning unfamiliar vocabulary.

- Advanced - advanced level. The language learner can actively discuss familiar and new topics. Understands texts of different genres and trends, uses context as an identifier for unfamiliar vocabulary. With this level of knowledge, it is assumed that the language learner can write long texts using different grammatical structures.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Competence is a professional level. The speaker freely communicates on various topics. Feels confident in debates and discussions, knowledge is close to the level of a native speaker. At this stage of language learning, a quick orientation in a new language is the state of the

language on various topics. Working with text is also related to relying on context. The level of proficiency includes writing detailed tests on specific topics with the correct use of terms, grammatical structures and punctuation.

Description of the various methods of teaching English This is the most relevant and intensive method of learning the language in today's and rapidly changing world. Today, the consumer can choose training for every taste - English for lawyers, English for economists, business English, etc. With this approach, listeners are given a lot of formulaic phrases and clichés. Yes, this makes it possible to navigate in the working environment, but is the language base and language sense really formed? This question remains open.

Linguo-sociocultural method of language learning. This method is a systematic approach aimed at studying the cultural and social environment without the goal of "dry" assimilation of lexical features and grammatical structures. The linguosociocultural method lifts the veil of stylistic coloring and vitality of the language. The two verbs, do and do, are good examples. Their main difference is that the verb to do means a creative approach to business, deliberate actions.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One of the authors of the methodology is S.G. Ter-Minasov. The scientific interests of the professor, like a puzzle, create a picture of this method of learning the language. These are the morphology and syntax of the language, stylistics, lexicology and lexicography, linguopoetics (how it sounds!), cultural anthropology, etc.

The purpose of this method of language learning is to enable the student to sufficiently understand the interlocutor, to feel the specific features of the language from the point of view of culture and ethics.

Communicative method of learning English. This approach is most common during the emergence of various language courses and trainings. These tutorials are for the use of this technique only. Using this method works very well abroad.

It is concluded that course participants actively participate in the process and learn to perceive foreign speech. Speaking and listening take up most of the study time. This method involves the artificial recreation of the language environment. The purpose of the communicative method is to help students overcome the language barrier, to teach course participants to first speak the language, and then think in this language. This gives the teacher the opportunity to plan the teaching of different groups of students / students with different needs, levels of knowledge and worldviews.

An emotional-semantic approach to learning English is a situation in which the teacher freely communicates with his students. This allows students to avoid intimidation by the teacher and the audience. The school of Galina Kitaigorodskaya and Igor Shekhter works according to this method.

The essence of the technique lies in the fact that students learn in the environment of modeling "legends" and situations created by themselves.

Basic approach to language learning. This method is widely used in universities and language schools. The essence of the methodology is to create an unshakable knowledge base "from small to large." Learning a language by the classical method is most relevant in a situation where the language has not been previously studied. A classic ... is to set phonetics, create a clear idea of the grammatical structure of the language, systematically increase vocabulary and

confidently introduce the student to listening. The classical method includes classes with a teacher who knows the native language of the student. The classical program, according to which Greek and Latin were taught in ancient times. This method can be called the "fortress occupation plan". The English teacher tries to give the student phonetics, syntactic constructions, vocabulary, grammar, etc. It should be noted that learning the fundamental method is slow and can last 2-3 years or more.

English is a compulsory subject in primary and secondary schools. During this period, students acquire basic knowledge of the English language, learn the alphabet, expand vocabulary and learn to read short texts. The method of teaching English in schools is almost always the same and is based on the curriculum approved by the Ministry of Education. Almost all teachers often use a communicative approach when teaching younger students. But in order to make the lessons more effective, some use additional techniques and methods that make the lesson more interesting and interesting.

How to make an introductory English course both effective and interesting for students? What methods can be used in the lesson? You will learn about this and much more from our publication.

CONCLUSION

Classical Teaching Methods English has been practiced in high school for many years. They are based on the grammar-translation approach. The basis of each lesson / sub-course is the grammatical part of the English language, explained in Russian. The teacher actively works with students and explains the main points. In turn, students study the rules, work with the text, perform exercises to consolidate it. But with too much theory, students often get lost and fail to develop speaking skills. Therefore, this method is effective only in combination with communicative and other approaches. An elementary English course on communication methods involves the development of children's skills such as writing, reading, listening and, of course, oral communication. In addition, lessons, like assignments, have a real theme: dialogues and texts on the topic of family, weather, school, hobbies, work, etc.

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